

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotation.

In this article, we can see the role and important aspects of social networks in the organization of classes using active interactive methods in teaching English.

Key words.

Interactive methods, communication skills, social networks, learning styles, collaboration, traditional learning.

Introduction

In today's increasingly globalized era, the demand for teaching a foreign language is also increasing. Everyone has an inner desire to learn a foreign language. By knowing a foreign language, you can travel to different countries, do business, and establish contacts with foreign friends. Today, thorough teaching of at least one foreign language is being started in Uzbekistan, starting from kindergarten and elementary school students. Various textbooks and interactive methods are being developed for them. Also, pedagogical skills of teachers are being improved.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Increased student engagement: Active and interactive methods encourage students to participate actively and engage in the lesson, helping them to stay focused and interested in learning.

Improved learning outcomes: Active and interactive methods help students to understand the concepts and ideas better, leading to improved learning outcomes and better retention of information.

Enhanced critical thinking skills: Interactive methods encourage students to think critically and creatively, helping them to develop problem-solving skills.

Increased motivation: Active and interactive methods help to create a positive learning environment, which can increase students' motivation to learn.

Better communication skills: Active and interactive methods require students to communicate effectively with their peers and teachers, helping them to improve their communication skills.

Increased participation: Active and interactive methods encourage students to participate in the learning process, which can lead to better engagement and understanding.

Enhanced teamwork and collaboration: Interactive methods often involve group work and collaboration, helping students to develop teamwork skills and work effectively with others.

Increased confidence: Active and interactive methods can help to improve students' confidence in their abilities and their communication skills, leading to better overall performance in English lessons.

Social networks can play a crucial role in the organization of English lessons, as they offer a range of benefits for both teachers and students. Here are some of the key ways in which social networks can enhance the teaching and learning experience:

1. **Increased engagement:** Social networks provide a platform for teachers to create interactive and engaging content that can capture the attention of students. This can include videos, quizzes, discussion forums, and more. By incorporating social media into lessons, teachers can make the learning experience more enjoyable and motivating for students.

2. **Collaboration:** Social networks enable students to collaborate with their peers, both inside and outside of the classroom. This can be particularly useful for group projects and assignments, as students can easily share ideas and resources with one another.

3. **Personalization:** Social networks allow teachers to personalize their lessons to meet the needs and interests of individual students. For example, teachers can tailor their content to match the learning styles of different students or create content that is relevant to their particular interests.

4. **Accessibility:** Social networks make it easier for students to access learning materials and resources. By posting content online, teachers can ensure that students can access it at any time, regardless of their location.

5. **Feedback:** Social networks enable teachers to provide feedback to students in real-time. This can be particularly useful for language learning, as teachers can correct mistakes and provide guidance as students practice their English skills.

Result And Discussion

Social networks can be a valuable tool for English language teachers looking to enhance their lessons and engage their students. By incorporating social media into their teaching strategies, teachers can create a more interactive, collaborative, and personalized learning experience for their students.

As an AI language model, it is not within my capacity to have personal experience in organizing English lessons. However, based on what I have learned from language experts, social networks can play a significant role in the organization of English lessons. Here are some ways in which social networks can be utilized:

1. Creating online groups: English teachers can create online groups on social networks like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn, where they can post lesson plans, share resources, and engage with their students.

2. Encouraging interaction: Social networks can provide a platform for students to interact with each other outside of the classroom. This can lead to more meaningful discussions, increased collaboration, and improved language skills.

3. Sharing multimedia content: Social networks allow teachers to share multimedia content such as videos, podcasts, and images, which can help to make lessons more engaging and interactive.

4. Building a community: Social networks can help to build a sense of community among students and teachers. This can lead to increased motivation, better learning outcomes, and a more enjoyable learning experience.

Overall, social networks can be a valuable tool in the organization of English lessons. By leveraging the power of social media, teachers can create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment for their students.

Acquiring communication skills in a foreign language is a very difficult task, because their acquisition involves the acquisition of various language subsystems to the extent that they are automatically used in self-communication. Therefore, the main task of a foreign language teacher is to create special conditions for the development of communication skills, the skills of interaction in different linguistic and social conditions, to train students from these language subsystems, but consists in teaching self-use. Such a task is extremely important in today's globalized world when young people want to communicate with representatives of other countries, ethnic groups, races, etc., because being able to speak a foreign language increases their self-confidence and self-esteem [1, 6].

Developing communication skills in a foreign language involves paying attention to understanding foreign speech and developing the ability to think simultaneously and speak in a foreign language when necessary. At the same time,

we should understand that the success of oral communication is influenced by a number of factors such as the age of students, their language development, the level of knowledge of a foreign language, and motivation [3, 144].

Traditionally, the process of learning a foreign language was carried out in the formal environment of the classroom. However, the rapid development of ICT, computer and Internet technologies is playing an increasingly influential role in learning English communication skills. More and more teachers are choosing to incorporate such technologies into their daily teaching practices because "technology can improve teaching." The impact of IR technology has led to the emergence of a process of communication between teachers and students outside the classroom. Computers and Internet technologies provide a wide range of synchronous and asynchronous communication known as "Computer Mediated Communication - CMC" [3, 144]. This informal learning process is growing in popularity and offers teachers and students a variety of resources that can be combined to create individual and student-tailored programs based on their learning opportunities. MOOCs (massive open online courses) are the latest trend in education, which are enriched by integrating various social media tools such as blogs and social networks (Facebook, Google, etc.) to increase student participation in the learning process and their knowledge. educational experience. In addition, they contribute to the study of special terminology in professional English [4, p. 118]. MOOC is one of the latest models of online education, which is becoming more and more popular. Although there is still no unified opinion on its definition and despite some criticism from experts, statistical data on the number of students of this type, the average satisfaction of teachers with the effectiveness of the educational process from its advantages indicates. One of them is a method that emphasizes the importance of social interaction, offers flexible learning materials, allows students to manage their learning process according to their personal needs and abilities [2, 444] and at the same time has a sense of belonging to a group. Social networks and online platforms are used to establish relationships between individuals with common interests. Users have the opportunity to share the opinions and interests of certain groups, which is especially important for those who do not have personal communication or who have the skills to develop an interaction strategy [5, 30]. Social networking technology offers more effective means of communication in educational contexts by enhancing personal interaction and fosters a sense of community among students.

Conclusion

So, today higher education is gradually taking "social networking technology" in the curriculum design. The transition from more traditional learning environment and social interaction to a more computer oriented educational environment can be a challenge and task for language teachers and students. Social medias are considered contextual interactive learning environment, and are popular among students, therefore, they are often integrated in the learning process on an academic platform. Such technologies provide educators with new mechanisms of activation of educational activity of students, development of the necessary foreign language communication skills. In addition to the ability to provide communication, interaction, flexibility in the learning content the social network can meet the students' individual needs.

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